

Turning E-waste into value: Innovative metal recovery using low-density concrete: Experiments and simulations

Mohammad Gheibi^{a,b,*}, Zahra Hajiahmadi^a, Martin Palušák^a, Daniele Silvestri^a,
Miroslav Černík^a, Mohammad Eftekhari^c, Stanisław Wacławek^a

^a Institute for Nanomaterials, Advanced Technologies and Innovation, Technical University of Liberec, Studentská 1402/2, 461 17, Liberec 1, Czech Republic

^b Faculty of Mechatronics, Informatics, and Interdisciplinary Studies, Technical University of Liberec, Liberec, Czech Republic

^c Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Sciences, University of Neyshabur, Iran

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Alkaline batteries
Concrete waste
Adsorption
Response surface methodology
Artificial neural network
Environmental impact assessment

ABSTRACT

The recovery of valuable metals from e-waste leachates is essential for advancing circular economy strategies and reducing environmental risks. This study examined Low-Density Concrete (LDC), a waste material, as a sustainable adsorbent for the recovery of Ni²⁺, Mn²⁺, Zn²⁺, and Fe²⁺/Fe³⁺. This is the first study that evaluated the performance of LDC in metal recovery from a leachate produced by the anaerobic digestion of alkaline batteries and municipal solid waste. The one-factor-at-a-time method was employed to find the effect of the pH and adsorbent mass on the results. The adsorption behavior was then studied using three different isotherm models: Freundlich, Langmuir, and Temkin. The findings indicated that pH significantly influenced metal removal, with ion exchange predominating in acidic conditions (pH < 5) and adsorption-precipitation mechanisms becoming more significant near neutral pH. Optimal performance was achieved at pH = 7 and an adsorbent mass of 0.10 g. The most significant parameter influencing metal removal efficiency was pH, as determined by ANOVA. To enhance process prediction, both Response Surface Methodology (RSM) and Artificial Neural Network (ANN) models were developed. ANN had a better predictive accuracy ($r > 0.98$) than RSM. Material characterization techniques such as FTIR, SEM-EDS, and TGA confirmed metal uptake and associated surface and structural changes. Finally, an environmental impact assessment using the Leopold Matrix indicated that LDC exhibits lower environmental impacts compared to conventional adsorbents. These findings support the potential of LDC as a green and low-cost material for metal recovery from complex e-waste leachates.

1. Introduction

Electronic waste (e-waste) is the fastest-growing solid waste stream worldwide [1–3]. Despite its rapid growth, only 17.4 % of the 53.6 million t of e-waste generated globally in 2019 was collected and appropriately recycled [4]. Under conventional waste management techniques, e-waste is often dumped in landfills, where heavy metals can be released through biological processes. These pollutants can then seep into groundwater, posing serious risks to human health and the environment [5]. Alkaline and non-rechargeable batteries, among e-waste categories, are often disposed of inappropriately, increasing environmental contamination. Moreover, the management of their environmental impacts remains inadequate, especially in developing countries. Each person in the United States uses about 10 alkaline batteries per

year, and over 671 million non-rechargeable batteries are sold annually in Canada. In the United Kingdom, waste from alkaline batteries reaches approximately 12 t within a year [6]. As a result, metals such as Cd²⁺, Ni²⁺, Zn²⁺, Cu²⁺, Pb²⁺, Cr⁶⁺/Cr³⁺, and Hg²⁺ are commonly detected in leachate from Municipal Solid Waste (MSW) landfills. Many of these metals originate from discarded batteries. Over time, these hazardous materials can migrate into soil, groundwater, and surface water, and have negative effects on the environment and public health [7]. However, these metals can also be recovered, which provides environmental and economic benefits. For example, recovering metals such as Zn²⁺ from alkaline battery waste can support waste management and can also be financially advantageous. Nevertheless, this option should be selected based on a thorough technical and economic assessment. Life cycle cost analysis and material flow analysis are common techniques

* Corresponding author at: Institute for Nanomaterials, Advanced Technologies and Innovation, Technical University of Liberec, Studentská 1402/2, 461 17, Liberec 1, Czech Republic.

E-mail address: mohammad.gheibi@tul.cz (M. Gheibi).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rechem.2026.103170>

Received 17 November 2025; Accepted 22 February 2026

Available online 26 February 2026

2211-7156/© 2026 The Author(s). Published by Elsevier B.V. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

used to identify cost-effective methods in solid waste management [8]. The primary goal of e-waste management is to recover and separate heavy metals. Selective recovery is especially important because different metals have different economic values. For example, Yousefi et al. [6] reported that recovering Zn^{2+} from discarded alkaline batteries can be economically attractive due to its high value. Their cost-benefit analysis estimated the recovery value of Zn^{2+} at 73.1 USD/kg. Therefore, efficient separation processes are essential [9]. There are several methods for heavy metal recovery, including adsorption [10–14], membrane separation [15], electrochemical recovery [16], and bio-leaching technologies [17]. Each approach possesses distinct advantages and limits contingent upon the application. Among these technologies, adsorption is acknowledged as an effective and cost-efficient technology, particularly due to its operational simplicity. Utilizing economical and waste-derived adsorbents can enhance the sustainability of this method [18].

The global amount of Construction and Demolition Waste (CDW) has increased substantially due to the widespread use of concrete materials and rapid urbanization, with an estimated 35 % of it being landfilled [19,20]. The environmental consequences of the generation, disposal, and recycling of CDW have emerged as a global issue [21]. This issue has gained increasing attention due to technological advancements and the growing focus on circular economy objectives. However, most research has primarily focused on the end-of-life stage of these wastes. Notably, adsorption presents a sustainable approach for reusing these wastes within the circular economy framework [22]. Highly alkaline concrete fines are rich in portlandite and calcium silicate hydrate (C–S–H). Dissolution of these phases releases Ca^{2+} and OH^- ions, increasing the pH of the solution, often above 10. Under such alkaline conditions, heavy metal ions (M^{2+}) can interact with deprotonated surface groups ($Si-O^-$ and $Al-O^-$) on hydrated cement phases through several mechanisms. These mechanisms include: (1) ion exchange with Ca^{2+} in C–S–H and partial substitution in ettringite; (2) inner-sphere complexation (chemisorption); (3) coprecipitation as $M(OH)_2$ or $Ca-M-CO_3$; and (4) flocculation through hydrolytic bridging [22]. This multidimensional mechanism forms the basis of the adsorption hypothesis, which is further examined in the following sections of this study.

Qasem et al. [23] compared wastewater treatment methods based on four key factors: cost-effectiveness, technical maturity, environmental friendliness, and automaticity. Adsorption stands out as highly cost-effective and mature, showing its established use and affordability. It is also rated highly in environmental friendliness, making it an eco-friendly option. However, adsorption scores lower in automation, indicating that it may require more manual involvement compared to other methods. For this reason, many studies have investigated materials that are selective for the recovery of specific metals. For example, Fang et al. [24] produced a thiolated β -cyclodextrin (T-CD) for gold recovery from acidic e-waste. In another study, Wei et al. [25] synthesized a Cu^{2+}/Fe^{2+} bimetallic composite ($Cu^{2+}/Fe^{2+}/rGO$) to remove Pb^{2+} ions from water. Robeck and Horn [26] employed a silica adsorbent functionalized with amino-polycarboxylate ligands to study the competitive adsorption of Ni^{2+} and Co^{2+} . They investigated the effects of pH, temperature, and metal ion concentration on selective metal separation, with the goal of improving battery recycling processes. It can be seen that most studies have used synthetic or chemically modified adsorbents. While effective, these adsorbents are often expensive and also generate secondary pollutants during their synthesis. Therefore, the adsorption based recovery of heavy metals from water resources requires further investigation and optimization [27]. Waste-derived adsorbents are a possible substitute in this regard, especially those made from CDW such as LDC, which is abundant and compatible with circular economy principles.

Unlike many waste-based adsorbents (e.g., agricultural residues) that primarily bind metal ions through surface adsorption and functional group interactions, LDC contains reactive cement hydration products that enable heavy metal removal through coupled adsorption and

chemical immobilization mechanisms. Due to its high alkalinity and the presence of Ca^{2+} and ion-exchangeable phases, LDC may provide more stable metal uptake through processes such as ion exchange and precipitation [28]. Moreover, LDC is a promising alternative for alleviating environmental challenges due to its low cost. This strategy supports a circular economy approach by enabling the recovery of heavy metal ions from landfill leachates, which is the focus of the present study. The application of LDC is an example of circularity in water treatment processes and supports several sustainable development goals [29]. Although several studies have demonstrated the metal removal potential of LDC, its performance under realistic conditions remains insufficiently explored.

Machine learning has emerged as a powerful instrument for analyzing complex multi parameter systems [30], particularly as advances in interpretable modeling and explainability techniques continue to accelerate. Recent studies have applied machine learning to predict the carbon-to-nitrogen (C/N) ratio of organic waste in MSW [31] and to model the heating value of MSW [32]. Specifically, Dehghan et al. [31] used machine learning models to estimate the carbon-to-nitrogen (C/N) ratio of organic waste in Mashhad. Their predictions were based on physicochemical characteristics collected from 17 cities, including moisture content, ash content, pH, and organic fraction. Among the evaluated models, the Extra Trees algorithm demonstrated the best predictive performance, with R^2 values of 1.0 for training and 0.97 for testing. SHAP analysis further revealed that ash content (%) was the most influential factor affecting the prediction of the C/N ratio. Baziar et al. [32] applied several machine learning models (XGBoost, Extra Trees, and CatBoost) alongside Multiple Linear Regression (MLR) to predict the heating value of MSW. The models used elemental composition and sample properties as input variables, including dry weight and the contents of C, H, O, N, S, and ash. The Extra Trees model exhibited the best performance ($R^2 = 0.999$ for training and 0.979 for testing) with the lowest prediction errors. Feature importance analysis showed that N content was the most significant predictor, followed by S, ash, and dry sample weight. Despite these advances, no studies have yet reported the prediction of heavy metal adsorption performance for LDC. Therefore, the present study employs ANN to evaluate and forecast the adsorption performance of LDC for heavy metal removal from leachate of e-waste samples.

There are many methods for optimizing the adsorption process, including One-Factor-At-a-Time (OFAT) [33], Taguchi, RSM, and other metaheuristic algorithms. Typically, OFAT is used as an initial screening tool, while RSM enables Sensitivity Analysis (SA) and interaction-based optimization using the experimental dataset.

The present study aims to optimize the recovery of heavy metals using LDC through a multi-step approach. Initially, alkaline batteries are subjected to biodigestion under simulated landfill conditions in the presence of MSW. The adsorbent is subsequently characterized using Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) Spectroscopy, Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM), Energy Dispersive X-ray (EDS) Spectroscopy with elemental mapping, and Thermogravimetric Analysis (TGA). Key operational parameters, including pH, mass of adsorbent, and contact time, are optimized using the OFAT method on samples. Furthermore, adsorption isotherms for Ni^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , and Fe^{2+}/Fe^{3+} ions are evaluated using Freundlich, Langmuir, and Temkin models. Historical data analysis is applied within the RSM framework to assess parameter sensitivity and perform interaction-based optimization using OFAT outcomes. In addition, ANN modeling is utilized to predict adsorption performance with improved accuracy. Finally, the potential environmental impacts of employing LDC as an adsorbent are evaluated using the Leopold Matrix (LM).

2. Methodology

The leachate of e-waste was prepared by anaerobic digestion of landfill waste in the laboratory, and the samples were analyzed for

heavy metals and Volatile Fatty Acids (VFAs) content. The commercial LDC was applied as an adsorbent, and its characteristics were evaluated using various analytical tools. The adsorption behavior of heavy metals on LDC was determined through batch adsorption experiments. The data obtained from the OFAT analysis were used for RSM modeling and SA. Furthermore, the same experimental data were applied to an ANN model to predict adsorption performance in complex environments. Finally, an Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) model was developed to determine the eco-compatibility of the adsorbent.

2.1. Material and instruments

Biological MSW was collected from bins at the Institute for Nanomaterials, Advanced Technologies and Innovation, TUL, Liberec, Czech Republic. In addition, 10 small alkaline batteries with a nominal voltage of 1.5 V were used as e-waste. Hydrochloric acid (37%) and sodium hydroxide ($\geq 97.0\%$), purchased from Sigma-Aldrich, Darmstadt, Germany, were used to control pH.

The applied LDC was provided by the Aerated Autoclaved Concrete section of PARIN-BETON Company in Mashhad City, Iran [34].

The FTIR spectra, with a resolution of 4 cm^{-1} covering the range of $4000\text{--}400\text{ cm}^{-1}$, were obtained using a germanium ATR crystal (NICOLET IZ10, Thermo Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA) equipped with a horizontal ATR accessory featuring a single reflection angle of 45° . The morphology of the applied LDC was observed using a Tescan Vega XMU SEM (TESCAN s.r.o., Brno, Czech Republic) equipped with EDS and mapping capabilities. The heavy metal concentrations were determined using ICP-MS (PerkinElmer, NexION 300D). The thermogravimetric properties were measured using a TG 209 F3 Tarsus instrument (Netzsch, Selb, Germany). The VFAs were measured by an HPLC chromatographic analyzer (UltiMate 3000, Thermo Fisher Scientific, Czech Republic) [35].

2.2. Leachate production

Leachate from MSW was obtained using a glass reactor with a capacity of 5 L based on the NEN 7343 standard [36]. The NEN 7343 standard describes the tank leaching test (also called the Dutch diffusion test), which is used to assess the release of inorganic contaminants from monolithic or granular solid materials over time. About 200 g of fruit peels (banana, orange, and apple), 400 g of food waste (chicken, bread, and rice), 100 g of tea waste, and 200 mL of energy drinks were added to the reactor. After mixing, 10 small alkaline batteries were added to the reactor, and the cap was closed to achieve anaerobic conditions. After 20 days under these conditions, the leachate obtained was filtered using Whatman® quantitative ashless filter paper (Grade 42) to remove suspended solids. A total volume of around 500 mL of leachate was collected. The concentrations of released heavy metals in the leachate were measured by ICP-MS. The schematic representation of the applied anaerobic digestion and leachate generation processes is shown in Fig. 1: ESI.

2.3. Adsorption procedure and isotherm determination

Before the adsorption experiments, the crushed and sieved LDC adsorbent was washed three times with distilled water and then oven-dried at 80°C for 24 h. Batch adsorption experiments were conducted at room temperature using 5 mL of filtered e-waste leachate. The effects of solution pH and adsorbent mass on the adsorption process were investigated by adjusting the pH to 2, 5, and 7 and using 0.10 and 0.15 g of LDC. All adsorption processes were performed using a magnetic stirrer at 500 rpm for 180 min (Table 1). All experiments were conducted in duplicate. After the reactions, a specific volume of the sample was collected and centrifuged at 10,000 rpm using an MPW Med. Instruments centrifuge to separate the solid and liquid phases. The concentrations of metals in the samples were determined by ICP-MS. The

Table 1

Experimental parameters and their investigated values.

Parameter	Values
pH	2, 5, 7
Adsorbent mass	0.10, 0.15 g
Contact time	180 min
Volume	5 mL

adsorption capacity (q) and removal percentage (R) were evaluated according to Eqs. 1 and 2 [37].

$$q = \frac{V(C_0 - C_e)}{M} \quad (1)$$

$$R (\%) = \frac{C_0 - C_e}{C_0} \times 100 \quad (2)$$

where q is adsorption capacity (mg g^{-1}), C_0 initial concentration (mg L^{-1}), C_e concentration after adsorption (mg L^{-1}), V volume of liquid (L), and M mass of adsorbent (g).

In the following, the adsorption behavior of different heavy metals was assessed by Freundlich, Langmuir [38,39], and Temkin models in the optimal pH and adsorbent mass (g). The applied equations and models are summarized in Table 1: ESI.

2.4. Optimization process

The analysis of historical data in the RSM method was applied for SA and optimization of the adsorption. Design Expert 7.0.0 was utilized for mathematical modeling in this study. The general form of the mathematical equation used for curve fitting is demonstrated in Eq. 3 [40].

$$\begin{aligned} Z = & a_0 + a_1X_1 + a_2X_2 + \dots + a_nX_n + a_{12}X_1X_2 + a_{13}X_1X_3 + \dots + a_{1n}X_1X_n \\ & + a_{23}X_2X_3 + a_{24}X_2X_4 + \dots + a_{2n}X_2X_n + \dots + a_{(n-1)n}X_{n-1}X_n + a_{11}X_1^2 \\ & + \dots + a_{nn}X_n^2 \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

2.5. Machine learning model development

The ANN model was applied to predict the adsorption capacity of LDC as a function of heavy metal type (MT), mass of adsorbent, and pH value. The ANN model used a cascade-forward backpropagation network type architecture. This cascade-forward backpropagation architecture was selected because it enhances nonlinear mapping capability by allowing direct connections between input and output layers. This can improve learning efficiency and prediction performance compared with conventional feed-forward networks. In addition, the training function, adaptation learning function, and performance function were selected as TRAINLM, LEARNNGDM, and MSE, respectively [41].

TRAINLM, or the Levenberg-Marquardt algorithm, is an optimization method used to train neural networks. TRAINLM is widely recommended for small-to-medium datasets due to its fast convergence and strong predictive accuracy. This algorithm combines the gradient descent and Gauss-Newton methods to achieve fast convergence and high accuracy. LEARNNGDM, which stands for gradient descent with momentum, enhances the basic gradient descent algorithm by adding momentum, allowing for faster convergence and reduced oscillations during training. MSE (Mean Squared Error) is a commonly used loss function in neural networks that measures the average squared difference between predicted and actual values, providing an indicator of model accuracy. Likewise, the number of layers, number of neurons, and transfer function were set in 2 layers, 20 neurons, and TANSIG [42]. These were determined through trial-and-error tuning in MATLAB to minimize MSE while maintaining good generalization and avoiding overfitting. TANSIG refers to the hyperbolic tangent sigmoid transfer

function, which is commonly used as an activation function in ANN, particularly in the hidden layers. The TANSIG function is mathematically defined as Eq. 4 [43].

$$f(x) = \frac{2}{1 + e^{-2x}} - 1 \quad (4)$$

This function maps the input values to an output range $(-1 - +1)$.

All computations for the ANN model were implemented using the NN (Neural Network) tool in MATLAB 2019b, and model tuning was performed using a trial-and-error approach.

The ANN model was trained and tested using 20 experiments with three inputs: MT (1–4), pH (2–7), and adsorbent mass (0.10–0.15 g), to predict adsorption capacity (q_e , 0.013–60.52 mg g⁻¹). The dataset shows wide variation, making it suitable for ANN modeling.

2.6. Environmental impact assessment

In the final section of this study, the LM was employed for the EIA of various adsorbents used in decontaminating heavy metals. Based on the calculations, two different dimensions were defined for adsorbents and

their environmental aspects. The adsorbent actions were defined as {'Supply chain of materials', 'Operation of materials'} and the environmental factors were defined as {'Air Quality', 'Water Quality', 'Soil Quality', 'Human Health', 'Energy Consumption'}. In the model, two matrices were considered, including the Magnitude Matrix (MM) and the Importance Matrix (IM). The calculation steps are shown in Eq. 5. In this equation, the impact matrix (E) was obtained by multiplying the magnitude and importance matrices element by element. Then, the sum of the impact scores across all environmental factors for each project action (OIA_i) was computed. In the following, the sum of the impact scores across all project actions for each environmental factor (OIF_j) was analyzed. Finally, the total environmental impact by summing all elements of the impact matrix (TEI) was computed [44]. All the computations and algorithms were executed in MATLAB 2019b.

$$E_{ij} = M_{ij} \times I_{ij}, OIA_i = \sum_{j=1}^m E_{ij}, OIF_j = \sum_{i=1}^n E_{ij}, TEI = \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^m E_{ij} \quad (5)$$

Fig. 1. The characterization analysis of LDC based on (a) SEM image with 25,000 \times magnification, (b) EDS, (c) O-elemental map, (d) Si-elemental map, (e) Al-elemental map, and (f) FTIR.

3. Results and discussions

3.1. LDC characterization

The characteristics of the LDC material used as an adsorbent are demonstrated in Fig. 1. As Fig. 1a shows (at a magnification of 25,000 \times), LDC adsorbent has a highly porous microstructure, which significantly increases the surface area available for adsorption. Such a structure is ideal for trapping and retaining particles or ions, which is crucial for applications in filtration or environmental remediation [45]. Furthermore, the surface of the LDC adsorbent is characterized by an irregular and rough texture. This morphology augments the effective surface area and may facilitate faster adsorption kinetics by providing numerous active sites for adsorbent-adsorbate interactions [46,47].

Fig. 1b displays an EDS spectrum, highlighting the complex composition of LDC and the ubiquitous distribution of the elements in the analyzed material. Prominent peaks are observed for O at around 0.5 keV, Mg at 1.25 keV, Al at 1.5 keV, Si at 1.75 keV, and Ca at about 3.7 keV. However, according to Table 2: ESI, O, Ca, and Si have the maximum weight percentages in LDC equal to 46.9%, 24.4%, and 18.4%, respectively. Likewise, Al, with around 2%, is one of the most essential elements in the LDC structure, which influences the adsorption process of heavy metal ions [48]. The maps of element distributions in EDS mode for O, Si, and Al are illustrated in Fig. 1(c–e). The maps of other elements are depicted in Fig. 2: ESI.

The FTIR spectrum analysis is depicted in Fig. 1f. The broad bands at 3409 cm^{-1} are mainly associated with the O–H stretching vibration due to water adsorbed in the sample. The bands in the 1639 cm^{-1} region may be attributed to the C=O stretching vibration of the carbonyl group in the LDC [49]. In addition, the asymmetric stretching mode of calcite/ aragonite is observed at 1413 cm^{-1} [47]. Fig. 1f shows that the symmetric stretching of Si–O–Si appears at 960 cm^{-1} , exhibiting a partial shift [50]. CO_3^{2-} anions are indicated at 873 cm^{-1} [47]. Additionally, compounds of calcium silicate hydrate are identified near 565 cm^{-1} [50,51]. The Si–O rocking vibration band is evident at 441 cm^{-1} [50,51]. The peaks at $\sim 410 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ may be related to the metal–O stretching vibration modes [52].

3.2. Leachate composition

After 20 days under these conditions, the filtered leachate was measured by ICP-MS to determine the concentrations of contaminant metals and other elements (Table 3: ESI). The released elements are categorized into three groups based on their concentration levels. In the anaerobic digestion of MSW, heavy metals are primarily released during the initial stages of hydrolysis and acidogenesis. During hydrolysis, complex organic materials are broken down into simpler soluble compounds, which can lead to the solubilization of heavy metals that are bound within these materials [53]. This process continues in the acidogenesis stage, where organic compounds are further broken down into VFAs and alcohols, creating an acidic environment. The acidification increases the solubility of heavy metals, as acidic conditions can dissolve metal salts and enhance their release into the liquid phase [54]. Factors such as pH levels, the composition of organic matter, and the presence of chelating agents can influence the extent of heavy metal release [55]. It can be observed that the maximum concentration is related to total Fe (2025 mg L^{-1}), including Fe^{3+} and Fe^{2+} , and K^+ (5785 mg L^{-1}) ions, which are related to the presence of food wastes. Similarly, the presence of Na^+ (720 mg L^{-1}) can be attributed to food waste decomposition [56]. The second concentration group consists of Zn^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , and Ni^{2+} at concentrations of 148.32 mg L^{-1} , 144 mg L^{-1} , and 20.6 mg L^{-1} , respectively. Finally, there are some trace elements such as Pb^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , and total Cr (Cr^{3+} and Cr^{6+}) with at

concentrations of 0.27 mg L^{-1} , 0.5 mg L^{-1} , 0.54 mg L^{-1} , and 0.13 mg L^{-1} , respectively. Although several metal ions were present in the leachate, Zn^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , and total Fe ($\text{Fe}^{2+}/\text{Fe}^{3+}$) were selected to evaluate their adsorption behavior onto LDC. The concentrations of Pb^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , $\text{Cr}^{3+}/\text{Cr}^{6+}$, Co^{2+} , and Ag^+ were detected only at trace levels ($\leq 1 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$) (Table 3: ESI) and were therefore not considered in the adsorption analysis. Although the concentrations of Na^+ and K^+ were relatively high, these ions are not classified as heavy metals and primarily originated from food-related sources.

3.3. Adsorption behavior of selected ions

According to adsorption behavior and also quantitative specifications of the ions, the recovery of Zn^{2+} [57], Mn^{2+} [58], Ni^{2+} [59], and total Fe (Fe^{3+} and Fe^{2+}) [60] was considered the main target of this study among the complex matrices. Batch adsorption experiments were performed using crushed LDC as the adsorbent, with varying mass of adsorbent and a fixed contact time of 180 min. Fig. 2a demonstrates the removal efficiencies of total Fe (Fe^{2+} and Fe^{3+}), Mn^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , and Zn^{2+} ions at different pH values. The removal of all metals reaches its maximum at pH = 7. This improvement can be attributed to the deprotonation of silica, an important structural component of LDC [61], which enhances the interaction between dissolved metal cations and the SiO_2 -rich surface [62]. At pH = 2, adsorption is mitigated by strong competition of H^+ ions at available adsorption sites. However, due to the higher affinity of LDC for metal ions, these ions can effectively displace H^+ [63]. Conversely, removal efficiencies decrease at pH = 5 for all investigated metals [64,65]. This reduction suggests a decrease in ion-exchange intensity and possible changes in the adsorbent's surface properties, making it less favorable for metal ion binding. Although Zn^{2+} maintains the highest removal percentage among the studied metals, its removal efficiency also declines significantly at pH = 5 [65]. Egboisiuba et al. [66] reported that Ni^{2+} adsorption onto diameter-controlled multi-walled carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs) was lowest at pH = 2 but increased significantly as pH rose toward 5. This behavior was attributed to the protonation of active sites under strongly acidic conditions, where abundant H^+ ions occupy adsorption sites and intensify competition with metal cations. With increasing pH, functional groups such as carboxyl and hydroxyl become deprotonated. This produces a more negatively charged surface and enhances electrostatic attraction toward Ni^{2+} ions. Chen et al. [67] confirmed that at pH > 6, Pb^{2+} and Cd^{2+} adsorption onto modified hydrochar increases significantly due to reduced H^+ competition and metal precipitation. The optimal pH for adsorption is above 6. This trend is consistent with the present results, where adsorption performance improved as pH increased to 7.

Adsorption of heavy metals onto LDC involves two mechanisms depending on pH. Below pH = 5, ion exchange dominates, where H^+ ions are replaced by metal ions due to LDC's stronger affinity for metals. This mechanism supports the assumption of ion exchange with Ca^{2+} in C–S–H or ettringite which is illustrated in the results of this investigation. Above pH = 5, adsorption and precipitation prevail, supported by reduced H^+ competition and the formation of stable metal hydroxides, enhancing removal efficiency through mono- or multi-surface interactions [68]. This mechanism also supports the hypothesis of coprecipitation as $\text{M}(\text{OH})_2$ or Ca–M–CO_3 . According to Huang et al. [69], metal ion adsorption occurs in three pH-dependent stages. In stage I (pH 1–7), M^{2+} and metal complexes like MNO_3^- and MOH^+ dominate, enhancing ion-exchange. Stage II (pH 7–9) sees reduced M^{2+} and formation of hydroxide complexes (e.g., $\text{M}_2(\text{OH})_2^{2+}$), with precipitation occurring. In stage III (pH > 9), $\text{M}(\text{OH})_3^-$ complexes form. A study by Blázquez et al. [70] demonstrated that the adsorption of Cr^{3+} onto an olive stone follows two different regimes of pH, $2 < \text{pH} < 4$ and $\text{pH} > 4$. Therefore, it can be concluded that when the adsorbent has a complex structure, like waste or natural materials, the adsorption process involves multiple mechanisms, supporting the findings of this study.

FTIR analysis further supports the role of silica-based structures and

Fig. 2. The removal percentage changes based on (a) pH changed: 2, 5, and 7, (b) mass of adsorbent: 0.1 g and 0.15 g for Ni²⁺, Mn²⁺, Zn²⁺, Fe³⁺ and Fe²⁺ ions, (c) SEM of adsorbent before adsorption, (d) SEM of adsorbent after adsorption, (e) TGA before adsorption, (f) TGA after adsorption, and (g) elemental composition and weight percentages of surface before and after the adsorption.

Condition for a and b: Temperature: 25 °C, time: 180 min, Volume: 5 mL with initial concentrations of Ni²⁺: 21 mg L⁻¹, Mn²⁺: 144 mg L⁻¹, Zn²⁺: 148 mg L⁻¹, Fe (Fe²⁺ and Fe³⁺): 2025 mg L⁻¹.

Condition for c-g: Temperature: 25 °C, time: 180 min, Volume: 5 mL, pH: 7, adsorbent: 0.1 g, initial concentrations of Al³⁺: 1.770 mg L⁻¹, As³⁺: 0.153 mg L⁻¹, Be²⁺: 0.007 mg L⁻¹, Ca²⁺: 65.602 mg L⁻¹, Co²⁺: 0.066 mg L⁻¹, Cr³⁺: 0.107 mg L⁻¹, Cu²⁺: 0.032 mg L⁻¹, Fe (Fe²⁺ and Fe³⁺): 803 mg L⁻¹, K⁺: Saturated, Mg²⁺: 39.327 mg L⁻¹, Mn²⁺: 54.726 mg L⁻¹, Na⁺: 2658 mg L⁻¹, Ni²⁺: 8.298 mg L⁻¹, Pb²⁺: 1.4 mg L⁻¹, Se⁴⁺: 0.559 mg L⁻¹, Zn²⁺: 54.1 mg L⁻¹.

pH-sensitive surface chemistry in adsorption performance. The band at 960 cm^{-1} corresponds to symmetric stretching of Si—O—Si, indicating a structural framework that can support ion exchange, particularly under acidic conditions. Limited adsorption at $\text{pH} = 2$ can be explained by protonation of surface groups (e.g., —Si—OH, —OH), which reduces metal binding. Also, the high concentration of protons competes strongly with metal cations for the adsorption sites. However, a portion of metal ions remains adsorbed due to residual affinity [71]. In addition, the contribution of C—S—H is relevant, as it can release Ca^{2+} and OH^- into solution, while H^+ substitution of Ca^{2+} under acidic conditions reduces the structural exchange capacity for metals [61]. As the pH increases toward neutrality ($\text{pH} = 7$), proton competition decreases [72] and surface groups undergo deprotonation, leading to the increase in negatively charged sites that favor electrostatic attraction with metal cations [66]. In this regime, structural changes reflected by the decreased intensity of the Si—O—Si band at 960 cm^{-1} suggest enhanced ion-exchange activity [71]. Additionally, higher pH conditions promote metal hydrolysis reactions. Fe^{3+} , for instance, undergoes hydrolysis above $\text{pH} = 3$ to form Fe—OH complexes and finally insoluble $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$ precipitates [12,71]. These hydroxides, inferred from the increased complexity in the 441 cm^{-1} Si—O rocking vibrations, are larger and provide more effective adsorption characteristics [73]. C—S—H also, at $\text{pH} = 7$, plays a crucial role by providing exchangeable Ca^{2+} with Fe (Fe^{2+} and Fe^{3+}), Zn^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , and Ni^{2+} . This result underscores the main role of pH in changing the chemical interactions at the adsorbent surface and enhancing the stability and efficiency of heavy metal ions removal.

Fig. 2b shows the influence of mass of adsorbent on metal removal at initial $\text{pH} = 5$. Increasing the LDC dosage from 0.10 g to 0.15 g enhances the removal percentage of all metals. This enhancement can be attributed to the greater availability of active surface sites at higher dosages, which facilitates more extensive interaction between the metal ions and the adsorbent, improving overall removal efficiency [61]. Nyirenda et al. [74] reported that increasing the adsorbent dosage enhanced the removal efficiency of Cu^{2+} , Pb^{2+} , Cd^{2+} and Zn^{2+} ions by using an activated carbon-supported silver-silica nanocomposite. This improvement was attributed to the greater number of accessible adsorption sites provided by the higher adsorbent mass, which promoted more effective metal ion uptake.

SEM images (Fig. 2c and d) provide additional evidence of adsorption performance via morphological changes. Before adsorption, the surface exhibited porosity and roughness (Fig. 2c), indicating abundant active sites for metal binding. Particle clumping suggests high surface energy and the presence of gaps and pockets that may increase adsorption capacity by trapping metal ions [75]. After adsorption (Fig. 2d), surface smoothing and densification are observed. This suggests that pollutants from the leachate, including organic matter and metal ions, were deposited on and coated the adsorbent surface. They occupied available active sites and reduced pore accessibility [76]. This behavior reflects effective adsorption in a complex matrix and may involve particle agglomeration caused by interactions between adsorbed metals and organic components such as VFAs [77]. Similar adsorption induced morphological changes have been reported by Belhassan et al. [12] for raw coal after removing heavy metals and organic pollutants, and by Jiang et al. [78] for magnesium hydroxide-based adsorbents, where pore filling was associated with enhanced contaminant uptake. This observation is consistent with the findings of the present study.

TGA analysis also indicates notable differences before and after adsorption (Fig. 2e and f). Before adsorption, the TGA curve shows a gradual weight loss up to $700\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. This includes a moisture-related loss or volatile evaporation around $105\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ [79], decomposition of organic matter at around $344\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ [80], and the breakdown of carbonate near $657\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ [80]. After adsorption, more weight loss occurs, particularly near $126\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. This suggests that more moisture or volatiles were adsorbed [81]. Multiple weight losses at $253\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, $333\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, and $354\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ indicate the adsorption of various organic molecules [82]. Significant losses at $\sim 561\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and $617\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ reflect the breakdown of carbonate [82]. This more

diverse decomposition behavior confirms that adsorption occurred in a highly complex environment, consistent with the findings of Zhou et al. [83]. The change in decomposition temperature, from $\sim 105\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ before adsorption to $\sim 126\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ after adsorption, shows that the material composition changed because wastewater components, especially organic matter, were adsorbed [84]. Additionally, residue mass decreases from 86.3% before adsorption to 72.6% after adsorption at $700\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, indicating increased material loss. This enhanced decomposition may be linked to breakdown of metal-organic complexes formed during adsorption, further confirming the presence of adsorbed contaminants. This outcome could also be attributed to greater surface area and pore volume [85].

EDS analysis (Fig. 2g) supports the uptake of metals and structural changes after adsorption. Prior to adsorption, the main constituents are Si (18.42 wt%), Ca (24.35 wt%), and O (46.90 wt%). The high Ca content suggests the presence of calcium carbonate or calcium silicate, which are key constituents of the adsorbent matrix and indicate a mineral- or silicate-based adsorbent structure. After adsorption, Ca decreases to 21.35 wt%, suggesting involvement of Ca sites in the adsorption, likely via ionic exchange. Notably, total Fe increases from 0.8 wt% to 4.09 wt%, K increases from 0.95 wt% to 1.83 wt%, and Zn becomes detectable at 0.19 wt%. Additionally, C content rises from 3.44 wt% to 5.1 wt%, supporting adsorption of VFAs and associated surface modification. The detection of heavy metals together with reduced Ca strongly indicates metal interaction with the adsorbent surface, while the increased C content implies the simultaneous adsorption of organic matter, which may influence metal binding through complexation effects. Inyangx et al. [86] demonstrated that the Pb^{2+} ions accumulated on the surface of biochar derived from anaerobically digested biomass after the adsorption process by EDS analysis.

3.4. Adsorption isotherm determination

The results of adsorption batch experiments at different initial concentrations of metallic sorbates were analyzed using different adsorption isotherm models. The results of the isothermal analysis are summarized in Table 2, Fig. 3(a-d): ESI, and Fig. 4(a-d): ESI. According to Table 2, based on the regression coefficients (R^2), the Freundlich model provides a better fit for the adsorption of all cations compared with the Langmuir and Temkin models. The Freundlich isotherm [87] is characterized by two parameters: K_F and n . A higher K_F value indicates a stronger interaction between the specific cation and the adsorbent surface. Among the studied ions, $\text{Fe}^{3+}/\text{Fe}^{2+}$ exhibited the highest K_F value, representing greatest adsorption. In contrast, Ni^{2+} showed the lowest adsorption, with a K_F value of only 0.02 mg g^{-1} , reflecting minimal adsorption onto the LDC surface. This suggests that the adsorption of all cations, including Zn^{2+} , $\text{Fe}^{3+}/\text{Fe}^{2+}$, Ni^{2+} and Mn^{2+} , onto the LDC surface occurs in a multilayer fashion [88]. The n value indicates adsorbent surface heterogeneity and the proportion of the high-energy active sites. The higher the n value, the more heterogeneous the surface. The value for the cations lies between 0.9 and 2.4, which is a normal value for

Table 2
Results of isothermal analysis in this investigation.

Two parameter isotherm	Parameter	Fe^{3+} and Fe^{2+}	Zn^{2+}	Mn^{2+}	Ni^{2+}
Langmuir	Q_{max}	8.97	1975.56	4.01	0.04
	K_{ads}	0.16	5.45×10^{-5}	0.02	0.99
	R^2	0.91	0.92	0.90	0.97
	n	6.06	0.97	2.10	2.35
Freundlich	K_F	3.37	0.09	0.34	0.02
	R^2	0.98	0.92	0.95	0.98
	A	12.87	10.63	12.18	9.00
Temkin	B	1.05	0.27	0.23	0.01
	R^2	0.94	0.73	0.80	0.91

similar materials [89–92] and indicates a medium capacity and heterogeneity of the adsorbent. Since the value of this coefficient characterizes the surface of the adsorbent, it should be the same for similar cations, which is true for the three cations except $\text{Fe}^{2+}/\text{Fe}^{3+}$. The difference for $\text{Fe}^{2+}/\text{Fe}^{3+}$ is probably due to the different valence of Fe^{3+} compared to the other Fe^{2+} . The maximum adsorption capacities of Ni^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , and $\text{Fe}^{2+}/\text{Fe}^{3+}$ ions based on the Langmuir equation were computed equal to 0.04 mg g^{-1} , 4.01 mg g^{-1} , $1975.56 \text{ mg g}^{-1}$, and 8.97 mg g^{-1} , respectively. The Langmuir constant denoted by K_{ads} (L mg^{-1}) can be used for the comparison of adsorption behavior of different metallic ions, evaluated as the separation factor (R_L), introduced by Webber and Chakkravorti [88] in Eq. 6.

$$R_L = \frac{1}{1 + C_0 K_{ads}} \quad (6)$$

where C_0 (mg L^{-1}) is the initial concentration of the adsorbate. A more beneficial adsorption process is indicated by a lower R_L value. To be more precise, the adsorption nature is classified as unfavorable ($R_L > 1$), linear ($R_L = 1$), favorable ($0 < R_L < 1$), or irreversible ($R_L = 0$) based on the R_L value for the given initial concentration. Based on the calculations, the results demonstrated that $0.007 < R_L\text{-Fe}^{2+}/\text{Fe}^{3+} < 0.06$, $0.997 < R_L\text{-Zn}^{2+} < 0.999$, $0.477 < R_L\text{-Mn}^{2+} < 0.892$, and $0.248 < R_L\text{-Ni}^{2+} < 0.651$. Therefore, the adsorption of all the metal ions on LDC was favorable. Also, Desta [93] illustrated that the adsorption of heavy metals ($\text{Cr}^{3+}/\text{Cr}^{6+}$, Cd^{2+} , Pb^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , and Cu^{2+}) onto activated teff straw with a range of 0.298–0.986 is favorable.

The heat of adsorption (b), which represents the bonding energy of the adsorbate-adsorbent interaction, was calculated as 247.75, 10.77, 9.17, and 2.35 kJ mol^{-1} for Ni^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , and $\text{Fe}^{2+}/\text{Fe}^{3+}$, respectively. These results suggest that physisorption is the dominant mechanism governing the adsorption of $\text{Fe}^{2+}/\text{Fe}^{3+}$ ions, whereas chemisorption predominates for Ni^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , and Zn^{2+} adsorption onto the LDC surface. This conclusion is supported by the fact that b values below 8 kJ mol^{-1} indicate physical interactions between the adsorbent and metal ions [94]. Among the studied cations, only $\text{Fe}^{2+}/\text{Fe}^{3+}$ exhibited a b value below this threshold. Unlike chemisorption, which involves the formation of strong chemical bonds, physisorption is driven mainly by weaker Van der Waals forces [95]. Therefore, these findings indicate that $\text{Fe}^{2+}/\text{Fe}^{3+}$ ions are probably adsorbed on the LDC surface through a more reversible and less energy-demanding mechanism, which is consistent with the observed adsorption behavior [96].

The results of acetate measurements before and after the adsorption process under optimal conditions are presented in Table 4: ESI. The analysis showed that acetate concentration decreased by approximately 17% (from 13,720 mg L^{-1} to 11,370 mg L^{-1}) during the adsorption process.

According to the study of Rotzinger et al. [97], in a bridging bidentate (μ) mode, the acetate ion adsorbs onto the metal oxide surface. Their FTIR analysis confirmed the presence of various metal oxide surface groups in the LDC material [97]. Both of the acetate carboxylate group's oxygen atoms align with two metal centers on the surface in this binding phase. Based on the results of vibrational spectroscopy, the monodentate mode was excluded and the chelating bidentate mode was judged unstable on the pentacoordinated metal centers. Furthermore, the observed spectral changes rule out simple electrostatic interactions and indicate a strong and specific interaction between acetate and the surface metal centers. By enabling each O atom to interact with distinct metal centers, the bridging bidentate mode provides efficient anchoring of acetate ions on the metal oxide surface and enhances adsorption stability [97]. It seems that the changes in the surface (Fig. 2c and Fig. 2d) could be related to the acetate reactions.

3.5. RSM analysis and ANN-based prediction of adsorption capacity

After conducting the adsorption experiments, the effects of pH and

mass of adsorbent were evaluated. Subsequently, RSM was applied to investigate the key factors (pH, mass of adsorbent (M), and MT) and to optimize the adsorption process.

For the prediction of adsorption on LDC using the effective features, the selected quadratic model is demonstrated in Eq. 7. Also, all terms of the formula for the prediction of q_e are presented in Table 3. According to Table 5: ESI, the quadratic RSM model was selected over the cubic model because it demonstrated better predictive reliability despite having a lower raw R^2 . While the cubic model showed a higher R^2 (0.89), its predicted R^2 was strongly negative (−0.60) and its PRESS value was larger (5547.4), indicating severe overfitting and poor out-of-sample prediction. In contrast, the quadratic model produced a less negative predicted R^2 (−0.31) and a lower PRESS value (4536.37), suggesting comparatively better generalization. Since R^2 tends to inflate as additional terms are added, relying solely on it can be misleading. Therefore, the quadratic model, with $R^2 \approx 0.7$, provides a more statistically defensible and practically reliable representation of the response surface trend. However, the predicted- R^2 of the selected quadratic model is negative, which indicates poor predictive ability and is therefore not acceptable. Also, Şahan [98] demonstrated that the adsorption of Pb^{2+} and Cu^{2+} onto enriched bentonite could be predicted with a quadratic model similar to the results of the present study. Therefore, in the following sections of this research, a more robust model is presented to develop an accurate mathematical model for the prediction of adsorption capacity based on the effective factors. Therefore, the main objective of applying ANN is to improve the predicted- R^2 value and enhance the prediction accuracy of LDC performance for recovering heavy metals from e-waste.

$$q_e = -2.02 + (8.21 \times \text{MT}) + (7.10 \times \text{pH}) + (1.38 \times \text{M}) \\ + (10.86 \times \text{MT} \times \text{pH}) - (0.98 \times \text{MT} \times \text{M}) + (8.82 \times \text{MT}^2) \\ + (8.73 \times \text{pH}^2) \quad (7)$$

Based on the ANOVA assessment of the experimental data in Table 3, it can be concluded that the mathematical model is significant and reliable for analysis, as indicated by a P -value of 0.02, which is less than the 0.05 threshold. Table 3 highlights that MT is the most critical factor in the model, with a P -value of 0.039. In the subsequent analysis, pH, with a P -value of 0.05, is considered more important than mass of adsorbent (M), which has a P -value of 0.64, in predicting adsorption capacity. These findings underscore the significance of MT and pH in influencing the adsorption process, guiding further research and optimization efforts. Eftekhari et al. [45] demonstrated that in the adsorption of Pb^{2+} and Cu^{2+} using polymer-modified concrete waste, pH is the most important factor compared to time and adsorbent mass. Likewise, Mohrazi et al. [99] demonstrated that the effects of pH changes in heavy metal ion adsorption onto modified calcined layer double hydroxide are significant and considerable.

Figs. 3(a-d) display a SA of the M-pH as operational parameters in the adsorption process for Ni^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , and $\text{Fe}^{2+}/\text{Fe}^{3+}$. $\text{Fe}^{2+}/\text{Fe}^{3+}$ ions, commonly found in various water resources, are generally

Table 3
The results of ANOVA technique in the presented model.

Source	Sum of Squares	Mean Square	F-Value	p-value
Model	2386.06	340.86	3.83	0.02
A-MT	472.4	472.4	5.31	0.039
B-pH	419.06	419.06	4.71	0.05
C-M	20.18	20.18	0.22	0.64
AB	544.83	544.83	6.13	0.029
AC	6.72	6.72	0.075	0.78
BC	0			
A ²	307.5	307.5	3.46	0.08
B ²	280.7	280.7	3.15	0.1
C ²	0			
Residual	1066.44	88.87		
Cor Total	3452.51			

Fig. 3. The outcomes of RSM analysis based on (a) Ni^{2+} : pH-M vs. q_e , (b) Mn^{2+} : pH-M vs. q_e , (c) Zn^{2+} : pH-M vs. q_e , (d) $\text{Fe}^{2+}/\text{Fe}^{3+}$: pH-M vs. q_e , and (e) normal distribution of responses.

Condition for a and b: Temperature: 25 °C, time: 180 min, Volume: 5 mL with initial concentrations of Ni^{2+} : 21 mg L⁻¹, Mn^{2+} : 144 mg L⁻¹, Zn^{2+} : 148 mg L⁻¹, Fe^{2+} and Fe^{3+} : 2025 mg L⁻¹.

considered less toxic and less expensive to treat compared to other heavy metals. However, due to their prevalence, understanding their behavior and competitive interactions in recovery processes is still important. In this study, the recovery of Fe^{2+} and Fe^{3+} ions was analyzed to investigate their competitive effects with other heavy metals. This is particularly relevant for leachates originating from batteries, which can release a mixture of metals, including $\text{Fe}^{2+}/\text{Fe}^{3+}$, into the environment. By studying Fe^{2+} and Fe^{3+} , this research aims to provide valuable insights into their impact on heavy metal recovery processes and their potential interference in treatment strategies [36]. As shown in Figs. 3(a-d), Ni^{2+}

and Mn^{2+} exhibit more pronounced fluctuations in the range of the response variable q_e compared to Zn^{2+} and $\text{Fe}^{2+}/\text{Fe}^{3+}$, as influenced by pH and mass changes. Moreover, across all four figures, it is evident that the variations in mass of adsorbent vs. q_e are less pronounced than those for pH vs. q_e , corroborating the results obtained from the ANOVA tests. Additionally, Fig. 3e demonstrates that the responses of the model (q_e) are distributed around a normal distribution, suggesting the model's adequacy and the normality of residuals in predicting the adsorption efficiency. This visualization effectively identifies potential overestimations within the model or inconsistencies in the experimental

setup, emphasizing the model's sensitivity and accuracy in reflecting experimental outcomes.

In this study, an ANN model was employed to predict q_e based on key factors (MT, mass of adsorbent, and pH), and it may provide better accuracy than the RSM model. The RSM model operates based on classical regression approaches, which cannot be readily implemented as an online system in water treatment processes. Therefore, the ANN model as an artificial intelligence approach could be applied as a real-time system for controlling optimal values based on prediction techniques.

Fig. 4a shows the performance of the ANN model over eight epochs. The training MSE (blue) decreases significantly, indicating effective learning behavior. The validation MSE (green) reaches its minimum at epoch 2 (1.3 MSE), marking the model's best performance before a slight increase, which suggests the onset of overfitting [100]. The test MSE (red) remains steady, showing the model's ability to generalize [101]. Epoch 2 is identified as the optimal stopping point to avoid overfitting and maximize results. Fig. 4b shows the performance evaluation of the ANN model predicting adsorption capacity over eight epochs, based on factors like MT, pH, and mass of adsorbent. It consists of three subplots, each displaying different performance measures. The model is getting close to a minimum in the loss landscape, or an ideal place for performance, according to the first plot, which charts the magnitude of gradient fall throughout the course of the epochs and culminates in a value of 0.499 at epoch 8. This gradient reduction indicates that the model's learning and parameter modifications are working well. Throughout the training process, the second subplot keeps the learning rate constant ($\mu = 0.01$), indicating that the ANN's algorithm may have a fixed learning rate setting or that adaptive rate tweaks are not necessary given the sufficient convergence. Red dots indicate the validation epochs in the final section of Fig. 4b, which shows the six validation checks carried out at the final epoch. This regular validation highlights a methodical way to monitor the model's performance and make sure it does not overfit while still generalizing well to new data. Taken as a whole, these indicators show a steady and efficient learning process, confirming the model's usefulness in forecasting adsorption capacities in different scenarios.

Fig. 4 (c-f) shows that the developed model achieved a Correlation Coefficient (CC) value more than 0.98 during both training and validation phases of the machine learning system. However, during the testing phase, this value decreased to around 0.8. Despite this reduction, all sections had a CC of approximately 0.98 for estimating adsorption capacity. This level of accuracy is not only acceptable, but it also solves the precision constraints of RSM used in this work. Fig. 4g illustrates a simplified ANN with an input layer of 3 neurons, a hidden layer with 20 neurons, and an output layer with 1 neuron. Each neuron uses weights (W), biases (b), and activation functions to process and transfer data, crucial for the network's learning and predictive capabilities. The mentioned structure could be applied for industrial application and for the purpose of smart management of the adsorption process in water treatment plants. In real-world conditions, operational factors such as reaction time, pH, and mass of adsorbent fluctuate, making process control complex. To address this challenge, the ANN model can be integrated with an alarm system, allowing for real-time monitoring and precise control of recovery performance. By continuously adjusting to dynamic changes in these parameters, the ANN model maintains optimal process efficiency and minimizes human intervention, thus enhancing the overall stability and reliability of the adsorption system [102,103]. Similarly, Juturu et al. [103] demonstrated that an ANN model could predict Cr^{6+} adsorption performance onto hematite nanoparticles with an overall CC more than 0.99. Likewise, Han et al. [104] depicted that the ANN model could estimate the adsorption efficiency of Cu^{2+} onto a metal-organic framework composite at different concentrations of the contamination with R^2 more than 0.99 which supports the outcomes of the present investigation. Claude et al. [102] showed that the R^2 of an ANN model for the prediction of Cu^{2+} adsorption efficiency onto sawdust was around 0.98. In their study, inputs of model were pH,

contact time, initial contamination dosage, and mass of adsorbent.

3.6. Life cycle-based environmental impact assessment of adsorbents

Following experimental evaluation of the adsorption process, RSM was applied for optimization and SA, while an ANN model was used to enhance predictive performance in heavy metal recovery. An EIA was then conducted to assess the environmental benefits of the developed adsorbent compared to commercial alternatives.

In this study, data on air, water, and soil quality, as well as human health and energy consumption, were collected from the Sustainable Material Management (SMM) Tool Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) [105] for the EIA conducted by LM. In this research, the evaluated adsorbent (LDC) is categorized as 'Other Concrete Products' while the alternative material was selected as 'Carbon and Graphite Products'. Graphene Oxide (GO) is frequently used for the decontamination of heavy metals [106] and is therefore considered a reference material for comparison. The raw data for both materials (LDC and GO) in the supply chain and operation sections are presented in Fig. 5a and Fig. 5b: ESI. In Fig. 5a and Fig. 5b: ESI, Smog Formation [107] is selected as a criterion for assessing the air quality impacts of both materials. Similarly, for water quality comparison, Freshwater Aquatic Ecotoxicity indicator values are used [108]. For soil pollution, Commercial Construction and Demolition Debris is selected due to the risk of landfill leachate affecting soil [109]. Additionally, Human Health - Respiratory Effects [110] are considered for assessing the potential health impacts of the materials. Finally, for energy assessment, an indicator from SMM is directly applied.

As part of the analysis, the importance variable matrix was determined (Fig. 5c and Fig. 5d: ESI). In the operation phase, the importance levels for both LDC and GO were considered equal to 1 across all environmental factors. This is because, during operation, various emissions may occur depending on the specific operational instructions, making all factors potentially significant. In the supply chain phase, the importance level of LDC was considered 1 point higher than GO. This is because, according to the literature review [47], there are greater risks of air pollution emissions associated with concrete production and processes. However, there is less evidence of such risks for GO. GO production significantly impacts freshwater ecotoxicity due to the extensive use of sulfuric acid in the Hummers method. During synthesis, around 170 mL of concentrated sulfuric acid is used per 5 g of graphite [111]. This poses a risk to water quality if released into aquatic environments, as sulfuric acid can contribute to water contamination and harm aquatic life, thereby necessitating careful waste management and containment [111]. Likewise, concrete production significantly impacts water quality by increasing pH from 4.8 to 7.9, while alkalinity rises by 3360%, Ca^{2+} by 640%, and K^+ by 700% [112]. However, because LDC is a secondary raw material and GO is a newly produced material, the importance variable for water quality was assigned one level higher to GO than to LDC. For the same reason, in both human health and energy consumption sections, the importance level of GO was considered one level more than LDC. It is worth noting that LDC is landfilled in larger amounts compared to GO, resulting in more interactions between soil and LDC. Therefore, the importance value of LDC was considered one level higher than GO for soil-related impacts.

Fig. 5 presents the results of the LM-based EIA technique for both GO and LDC. According to Fig. 5a and Fig. 5b, each material has distinct environmental impacts across their lifecycle phases. GO has a substantially higher influence on energy consumption during the operations (500) than LDC, which peaks at 400 in the supply chain phase. In terms of water quality, GO has a greater influence in the supply chain (167.8) than LDC (99.96). In terms of soil quality, LDC has a greater influence (262.5) within the supply chain than GO in the same category (182.6). Finally, it can be mentioned that the human health impacts of GO were computed more than LDC based on the assumptions of LM. As shown in Fig. 5a and Fig. 5b, during the operation phase, all impact categories for

Fig. 4. The ANN model details based on (a) MSE error trends in different epochs, (b) ANN indicators, (c) training R^2 , (d) validation R^2 , (e) test R^2 , (f) overall R^2 , and (g) ANN structure.

Fig. 5. The LM-EIA results based on (a) heatmap of LDC's impact matrix in both supply chain and operation sections, (b) heatmap of GO's impact matrix in both supply chain and operation sections, (c) air quality SA, (d) water quality SA, (e) soil quality SA, (f) human health SA, and (g) energy consumption SA.

GO were higher than those for LDC, except for soil quality.

In the SA, the initially selected key variables were multiplied by values ranging from 0.5 to 1.5. This method was used to investigate how changes in the prominence of specific attributes influence the overall environmental impact. According to Fig. 5 (c-g), GO consistently exhibited larger environmental impacts than LDC across all features. Notably, the analysis shows that as the significance variable in the SA for air and soil quality increases, the environmental impacts of both GO and LDC tend to converge. This shows that, as the relevance of these properties increases, the differences between the two materials become less noticeable. In contrast, in the areas of water quality, human health, and energy consumption, the curves depicting the environmental impacts of GO and LDC diverge. This suggests an increasing gap in their environmental implications as the significance of these qualities grows. The SA provides valuable insights for selecting materials in the adsorption of heavy metals. By understanding how changes in feature importance affect environmental impacts, decision-makers can make more informed choices regarding material selection, ensuring a balance between environmental sustainability and operational efficiency. Deng et al. [113] reported a Characterization Factor (*CF*) for GO freshwater ecotoxicity of 777.5 Potentially Affected Species (PAF) $\text{m}^3 \text{day kg}^{-1}$, with a fate factor of 27.2 days and an exposure factor of 0.93. Heteroaggregation was identified as the dominant GO removal process. Compared to mass-balanced models, colloidal models yielded lower fate factors (27.2 vs. 59.1 days). SA revealed a wide *CF* variation (~ 1 to 10^3 PAF $\text{m}^3 \text{day kg}^{-1}$), mainly due to limited toxicity data. Therefore, the results of the study provide evidence for using alternative waste-based adsorbents instead of GO to control environmental impacts and support circular economy initiatives.

The results of this study indicate that LDC can be practically applied as a low-cost and sustainable adsorbent for the recovery of heavy metals from e-waste leachates and similar contaminated waters. Owing to its wide availability as CDW, LDC can be readily integrated into landfill leachate treatment systems, battery recycling facilities, or industrial wastewater treatment units as a pre-treatment material. Effective metal removal at near-neutral pH conditions ($\text{pH} \approx 7$) reduces the need for extensive chemical pH adjustment. This simplifies operation and lowers

overall treatment costs. The developed ANN model exhibited high prediction accuracy, with a CC greater than 0.98. This performance level underscores its potential use in smart and automated treatment systems for real-time monitoring and optimization of adsorption operations. Future studies should concentrate on assessing the long-term efficacy of LDC via regeneration and multi-cycle adsorption tests. Moreover, adsorption kinetics at column-scale conditions must be examined to facilitate process scale-up. Integrating the ANN methodology with advanced optimization algorithms could enhance forecast precision and process regulation.

4. Conclusion

The performance of the LDC as an adsorbent for recovering heavy metals from e-waste leachates was evaluated in this study. Experimental results confirmed the efficient removal of Ni^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , and $\text{Fe}^{2+}/\text{Fe}^{3+}$. It was found that the adsorption of the mentioned metals strongly depends on the pH of the solution. At acidic conditions ($\text{pH} < 5$), metal removal was governed mainly by ion exchange with Ca^{2+} from cement hydration phases. At $\text{pH} = 7$, adsorption and metal hydroxide precipitation became the dominant mechanisms. Optimal performance was achieved at $\text{pH} = 7$, a mass of adsorbent of 0.10 g, and a contact time of 180 min. Isotherm analysis showed that the Freundlich model provided the best fit ($R^2 = 0.92\text{--}0.98$), indicating multilayer adsorption. Temkin analysis revealed that the adsorption of Ni^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , and Zn^{2+} happened predominantly via chemisorption, while $\text{Fe}^{2+}/\text{Fe}^{3+}$ adsorption was governed by physisorption. According to the RSM analysis results, pH was identified as the most significant parameter that influences adsorption capacity, followed by MT. However, mass of adsorbent showed a limited effect ($P = 0.64$) on adsorption capacity. The quadratic RSM model demonstrated insufficient predictive reliability, as evidenced by its negative predicted- R^2 despite achieving a moderate correlation ($R^2 \approx 0.70$). An ANN model was developed to overcome this constraint. The model's predictive performance was superior to that of RSM, as evidenced by the CC values of over 0.98 for the training, validation, and total datasets. EIA further showed that LDC exhibits lower impacts in water quality, human health, and energy consumption

compared to GO. These results confirm that waste-derived LDC combines high adsorption efficiency, robust predictive accuracy, and improved environmental performance. This supports its application as a sustainable and scalable solution for heavy metal recovery from e-waste leachates. Future investigations should integrate thorough kinetic modeling of the adsorption process to elucidate the rate-controlling processes. Furthermore, the incorporation of advanced optimization methods, including metaheuristic algorithms (e.g., genetic algorithms), could significantly improve process efficiency, facilitating better adsorbent dosage selection and overall system performance. This combined approach can enhance process efficiency and guide the scale-up of this sustainable metal recovery strategy for real-world applications.

Declaration

In the writing process of the present study, AI-assisted tools were employed to enhance clarity, structure, and overall quality.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Mohammad Gheibi: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Zahra Hajiahmadi:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Methodology. **Martin Paluśák:** Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Daniele Silvestri:** Writing – original draft, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Miroslav Černík:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Mohammad Eftekhari:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Methodology. **Stanisław Waclawek:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgement

This work was supported by the European Union's HORIZON EUROPE WIDERA 2021 program under the SURRI project, Grant Agreement No 101079345 as well as by the Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports of the Czech Republic and the European Union European Structural and Investment Funds in the frames of Operational Programme Research, Development and Education – project Hybrid Materials for Hierarchical Structures (HyHi, Reg. No. CZ.02.1.01/0.0/0.0/16_019/0000843).

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rechem.2026.103170>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

References

- [1] Tackling informality in e-waste management: The potential of cooperative enterprises, International Labour Organization, 2014. <https://www.ilo.org/publications/tackling-informality-e-waste-management-potential-cooperative-enterprises>.
- [2] Electronic waste (e-waste). [https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/electronic-waste-\(e-waste\)](https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/electronic-waste-(e-waste)), 2025.
- [3] Y. Li, Z. Huo, Y. Ying, L. Duan, C. Jiang, W. Chen, Effects of transient flow conditions on colloid-facilitated release of decabromodiphenyl ether: implications for contaminant mobility at e-waste recycling sites, *Eco-Environ. Health* 3 (2024) 317–324.
- [4] V. Forti, C.P. Balde, R. Kuehr, G. Bel, The Global E-Waste Monitor 2020: Quantities, Flows and the Circular Economy Potential, United Nations University/United Nations Institute for Training and Research, International Telecommunication Union, and International Solid Waste Association, 2020 <http://collections.unu.edu/view/UNU:7737> (accessed June 24, 2025).
- [5] E. Spalvins, B. Dubey, T. Townsend, Impact of electronic waste disposal on Lead concentrations in landfill leachate, *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 42 (2008) 7452–7458.
- [6] M. Yousefi, F. Khosravani, M. Farzadkia, A.H. Mahvi, M. Kermani, A. Esrafil, M. Gholami, Sustainable management of alkaline battery waste in developing countries by waste reduction and metal recovery development: a cost-benefit study based on waste flow analysis to select the optimum scenario, *Arab. J. Chem.* 16 (2023) 105140.
- [7] S. Karnchanawong, P. Limpitprakan, Evaluation of heavy metal leaching from spent household batteries disposed in municipal solid waste, *Waste Manag.* 29 (2009) 550–558.
- [8] M.T. Islam, N. Huda, Material flow analysis (MFA) as a strategic tool in E-waste management: applications, trends and future directions, *J. Environ. Manag.* 244 (2019) 344–361.
- [9] Z. Sun, Y. Xiao, J. Sietsma, H. Agterhuis, Y. Yang, A cleaner process for selective recovery of valuable metals from electronic waste of complex mixtures of end-of-life electronic products, *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 49 (2015) 7981–7988.
- [10] E. Allahkarami, E. Allahkarami, A. Azadmehr, M.E. Shahrabadi, Kinetics and statistical physics modeling of heavy metal ions adsorption onto functionalized pyrite composite: experimental and modeling, *Results Chem.* 17 (2025) 102536.
- [11] C.-Y. Hsu, Y. Ajaj, Z.H. Mahmoud, G. Kamil Ghadir, Z. Khalid Alani, M. M. Hussein, S. Abed Hussein, M. Morad Karim, A. Al-khalidi, J.K. Abbas, A. Hussein Kareem, E. Kianfar, Adsorption of heavy metal ions using chitosan/graphene nanocomposites: a review study, *Results in Chemistry* 7 (2024) 101332.
- [12] H. Belhassan, M. Merzouki, G. El mouhri, H. Amakdouf, O. Lamrani, E. Mehdi Haily, Y. Massaoudi, A. Boukir, M. Benlemlih, High efficiency removal of heavy metals and organic pollutants from brassware using raw coal: kinetic adsorption and optimized process, *Results Chem.* 5 (2023) 100855.
- [13] H.A. Hegazy, H.H. Moon, S. Perumal, M.R. Elmasry, J. Park, Y.-C. Kim, C. Song, Multifunctional imidazole-functionalized polyaspartamide/TiO₂ composites for UV screening, heavy metal removal, and suppressed photocatalytic activity, *Results Chem.* 18 (2025) 102765.
- [14] A. Rezagholizade-shirvan, Z. Hashami, S. Fallahzadeh, M. Mahmoudzadeh, Z. Rezaei, E. Shamloo, Eco-friendly bio-nanocomposite for efficient removal of heavy metals from a variety cookware: an innovative approach to food purification during cooking process, *Results Chem.* 18 (2025) 102841.
- [15] I.N.S. Kahar, N. Othman, N.F.M. Noah, S.S. Suliman, Recovery of copper and silver from industrial e-waste leached solutions using sustainable liquid membrane technology: a review, *Environ. Sci. Pollut. Res.* 30 (2023) 66445–66472.
- [16] Q. Song, Y. Liu, L. Zhang, Z. Xu, Selective electrochemical extraction of copper from multi-metal e-waste leaching solution and its enhanced recovery mechanism, *J. Hazard. Mater.* 407 (2021) 124799.
- [17] P.R. Yaashikaa, B. Priyanka, P. Senthil Kumar, S. Karishma, S. Jeevanantham, S. Indraganti, A review on recent advancements in recovery of valuable and toxic metals from e-waste using bioleaching approach, *Chemosphere* 287 (2022) 132230.
- [18] T.H. Bui, S. Jeon, Y. Lee, Facile recovery of gold from e-waste by integrating chlorate leaching and selective adsorption using chitosan-based bioadsorbent, *J. Environ. Chem. Eng.* 9 (2021) 104661.
- [19] K. Kabirifar, M. Mojtahedi, C. Wang, V.W.Y. Tam, Construction and demolition waste management contributing factors coupled with reduce, reuse, and recycle strategies for effective waste management: a review, *J. Clean. Prod.* 263 (2020) 121265.
- [20] M. Gheibi, S.R. Masoomi, M. Eftekhari, M. Akrami, M. Paluśák, D. Silvestri, M. Černík, S. Waclawek, Heavy metals adsorption using CDW adsorbents: a sustainable path for water purification, *J. Hazard. Mater. Adv.* 20 (2025) 100883.
- [21] T. Wang, J. Wang, P. Wu, J. Wang, Q. He, X. Wang, Estimating the environmental costs and benefits of demolition waste using life cycle assessment and willingness-to-pay: a case study in Shenzhen, *J. Clean. Prod.* 172 (2018) 14–26.
- [22] S. Pallewatta, M. Weerasooriyagedara, S. Bordoloi, A.K. Sarmah, M. Vithanage, Reprocessed construction and demolition waste as an adsorbent: an appraisal, *Sci. Total Environ.* 882 (2023) 163340.
- [23] N.A.A. Qasem, R.H. Mohammed, D.U. Lawal, Removal of heavy metal ions from wastewater: a comprehensive and critical review, *Npj Clean Water* 4 (2021) 36.
- [24] D. Fang, F. Bi, L. Yang, W. Hu, Z. Hua, H. Wei, C. Chen, Y. Tu, P. Shao, M. Li, X. Luo, G. Yang, Selective extraction of gold from strong acid E-waste leachate through H⁺-triggered cascade reaction of thiolated β-cyclodextrin, *Resour. Conserv. Recycl.* 193 (2023) 106958.
- [25] J. Wei, L. Ge, W. Wang, P. Hong, Y. Li, Y. Li, C. Xie, Z. Wu, J. He, L. Kong, Efficient remediation of heavy metal-contaminated water using a magnetically collectible nanoscale Cu/Fe/rGO primary battery, *J. Environ. Chem. Eng.* 12 (2024) 111574.
- [26] B. Robeck, H. Horn, Towards sustainable battery recycling: selective dynamic adsorption of nickel(II) and cobalt(II) in an adsorbent fixed-bed reactor at elevated temperature, *Discov. Chem. Eng.* 4 (2024) 1.

- [27] T.M. Alslaibi, I. Abustan, M.A. Ahmad, A.A. Foul, Application of response surface methodology (RSM) for optimization of Cu²⁺, Cd²⁺, Ni²⁺, Pb²⁺, Fe²⁺, and Zn²⁺ removal from aqueous solution using microwaved olive stone activated carbon, *J. Chem. Technol. Biotechnol.* 88 (2013) 2141–2151.
- [28] Q. Liu, P. Feng, L. Shao, C. Chen, X. Liu, Y. Ma, L. Zhang, G. Geng, Quantifying the immobilization mechanisms of heavy metals by calcium silicate hydrate (C-S-H): the case of Cu²⁺, *Cem. Concr. Res.* 186 (2024) 107695.
- [29] M. Kasprzyk, K. Czerwionka, M. Gajewska, Waste materials assessment for phosphorus adsorption toward sustainable application in circular economy, *Resour. Conserv. Recycl.* 168 (2021) 105335.
- [30] A. Sheikhmohammadi, S. Hosseinpour, Y. Maleki, M. Yousefi, A. Rezagholizadeh-shirvan, Artificial intelligence-enhanced optimization for methyl paraben removal from aqueous solutions using green-synthesized copper oxide nanoparticles on magnetic polyglucosamine/alginate biocomposites, *Results Chem.* 18 (2025) 102673.
- [31] A. Dehghan, V. Oskoei, T. Khajavi, M. Baziar, M. Yousefi, Machine learning-based prediction of the C/N ratio in municipal organic waste, *Environ. Technol. Innovation* 37 (2025) 103977.
- [32] M. Baziar, M. Yousefi, V. Oskoei, A. Makhdoomi, R. Abdollahzadeh, A. Dehghan, Machine learning-based prediction of heating values in municipal solid waste, *Sci. Rep.* 15 (2025) 14589.
- [33] N. Rezazadeh, Danesh, M. Shahnaz, Eftekhari, TX-100 adsorption from aqueous solution using modified graphene oxide; optimization by response surface methodology and one factor at a time techniques, *J. Dispers. Sci. Technol.* 44 (2023) 889–900.
- [34] Parin Beton - Leading Manufacturer of Autoclaved Aerated Concrete (AAC), Parin Beton (2026). <https://www.parinbeton.com/en/home/> (accessed June 24, 2025).
- [35] L.R.V. De Sá, M.A.L. De Oliveira, M.C. Cammarota, A. Matos, V.S. Ferreira-Leitão, Simultaneous analysis of carbohydrates and volatile fatty acids by HPLC for monitoring fermentative biohydrogen production, *Int. J. Hydrogen Energy* 36 (2011) 15177–15186.
- [36] S.M. Xará, J.N. Delgado, M.F. Almeida, C.A. Costa, Laboratory study on the leaching potential of spent alkaline batteries, *Waste Manag.* 29 (2009) 2121–2131.
- [37] D. Martemianov, B.-B. Xie, T. Yurmazova, M. Khaskelberg, F. Wang, C.-H. Wei, S. Preis, Cellular concrete-supported cost-effective adsorbents for aqueous arsenic and heavy metals abatement, *J. Environ. Chem. Eng.* 5 (2017) 3930–3941.
- [38] N.B. Mohamed, Y.M.N.S. Ismail, M.H.M. Noor, N.W.M. Rusli, N. Ngadi, Sustainable kaolin-modified carbon black from waste tires for crystal violet adsorption: insights from kinetic, isotherm, and thermodynamic analyse, *Appl. Mater. Today* 47 (2025) 102925.
- [39] F.S. Saeb, A. Salem, S. Salem, Spectroscopically study of competitive adsorption of planar and non-planar reactive dyes over magnesium oxide nanoparticles sustainably fabricated through autoignition, *Appl. Mater. Today* 44 (2025) 102689.
- [40] F. Mahmoudi Jalali, B. Chahkandi, M. Gheibi, M. Eftekhari, K. Behzadian, L. C. Campos, Developing a smart and clean technology for bioremediation of antibiotic contamination in arable lands, *Sustain. Chem. Pharm.* 33 (2023) 101127.
- [41] K. Suzuki, *Artificial Neural Networks: Architectures and Applications*, BoD – Books on Demand, 2013.
- [42] M.H. Hassoun, *Fundamentals of Artificial Neural Networks*, MIT Press, 1995.
- [43] **tansig - Hyperbolic tangent sigmoid transfer function - MATLAB**, (2025). <http://www.mathworks.com/help/deeplearning/ref/tansig.html> (accessed June 24, 2025).
- [44] F.A. Al-Nasrawi, S.L. Kareem, L.A. Saleh, Using the Leopold matrix procedure to assess the environmental impact of pollution from drinking water projects in Karbala City, Iraq, *IOP Conf. Ser.: Mater. Sci. Eng.* 671 (2020) 012078.
- [45] M. Eftekhari, M. Gheibi, H. Azizi-Toupkanloo, Z. Hossein-Abadi, M. Khraishah, A. M. Fathollahi-Fard, G. Tian, Statistical optimization, soft computing prediction, mechanistic and empirical evaluation for fundamental appraisal of copper, lead and malachite green adsorption, *J. Ind. Inf. Integr.* 23 (2021) 100219.
- [46] S. Liao, X. Wang, H. Yin, J.E. Post, Y. Yan, W. Tan, Q. Huang, F. Liu, X. Feng, Effects of Al substitution on local structure and morphology of lepidocrocite and its phosphate adsorption kinetics, *Geochim. Cosmochim. Acta* 276 (2020) 109–121.
- [47] M. Gheibi, M. Eftekhari, M.G. Tabrizi, A.M. Fathollahi-Fard, G. Tian, Mechanistic evaluation of cationic dyes adsorption onto low-cost calcinated aerated autoclaved concrete wastes, *Int. J. Environ. Sci. Technol.* 19 (2022) 6429–6444.
- [48] E.O. Ajala, M.O. Aliyu, M.A. Ajala, G. Mamba, A.M. Ndana, T.S. Olatunde, Adsorption of lead and chromium ions from electroplating wastewater using plantain stalk modified by amorphous alumina developed from waste cans, *Sci. Rep.* 14 (2024) 6055.
- [49] R.M. Silverstein, G.C. Bassler, *Spectrometric Identification of Organic Compounds*, ACS Publications, 1962.
- [50] Y. Liang, J. Ouyang, H. Wang, W. Wang, P. Chui, K. Sun, Synthesis and characterization of core-shell structured SiO₂@YVO₄:Yb³⁺, Er³⁺ microspheres, *Appl. Surf. Sci.* 258 (2012) 3689–3694.
- [51] E. Herth, R. Zeggari, J.-Y. Rauch, F. Remy-Martin, W. Boireau, Investigation of amorphous SiO_x layer on gold surface for surface plasmon resonance measurements, *Microelectron. Eng.* 163 (2016) 43–48.
- [52] P.T. Thu, V.D. Thinh, V.D. Lam, T.N. Bach, L.T.H. Phong, D.H. Tung, D.H. Manh, N. Van Khien, T.X. Anh, N.T.H. Le, Decorating of ag and CuO on ZnO nanowires by plasma electrolyte oxidation method for enhanced photocatalytic efficiency, *Catalysts* 12 (2022) 801.
- [53] M. Hussein, K. Yoneda, Z. Mohd-Zaki, A. Amir, N. Othman, Heavy metals in leachate, impacted soils and natural soils of different landfills in Malaysia: an alarming threat, *Chemosphere* 267 (2021) 128874.
- [54] M.M. Shahsavari, M. Akrami, M. Gheibi, B. Kaviani-pour, A.M. Fathollahi-Fard, K. Behzadian, Constructing a smart framework for supplying the biogas energy in green buildings using an integration of response surface methodology, artificial intelligence and petri net modelling, *Energy Convers. Manag.* 248 (2021) 114794.
- [55] S. Xie, Y. Ma, P.J. Strong, W.P. Clarke, Fluctuation of dissolved heavy metal concentrations in the leachate from anaerobic digestion of municipal solid waste in commercial scale landfill bioreactors: the effect of pH and associated mechanisms, *J. Hazard. Mater.* 299 (2015) 577–583.
- [56] M. Pawlett, M. Tibbett, Is Sodium in Anaerobically Digested Food Waste a Potential Risk to Soils?, 2015.
- [57] B. Ebin, M. Petranikova, B.-M. Steenari, C. Ekberg, Recovery of industrial valuable metals from household battery waste - Burçak Ebin, Martina Petranikova, Britt-Marie Steenari, Christian Ekberg, *Waste Manag. Res.* 37 (n.d.) (2019) 168–175.
- [58] A. Sobianowska - Turek, W. Szczepaniak, M. Zablocka-Malicka, Electrochemical evaluation of manganese reducers – recovery of Mn from Zn–Mn and Zn–C battery waste, *J. Power Sources* 270 (2014) 668–674.
- [59] J. Wang, Y. Zhang, L. Yu, K. Cui, T. Fu, H. Mao, Effective separation and recovery of valuable metals from waste Ni-based batteries: a comprehensive review, *Chem. Eng. J.* 439 (2022) 135767.
- [60] S. Virolainen, T. Wesselborg, A. Kaukinen, T. Sainio, Removal of iron, aluminium, manganese and copper from leach solutions of lithium-ion battery waste using ion exchange, *Hydrometallurgy* 202 (2021) 105602.
- [61] S. Praneeth, A. Zameer, N. Zhang, B.K. Dubey, A.K. Sarmah, Biochar admixture cement mortar fines for adsorptive removal of heavy metals in single and multimetal solution: insights into the sorption mechanisms and environmental significance, *Sci. Total Environ.* 839 (2022) 155992.
- [62] N. Kobylinska, L. Kostenko, S. Khainakov, S. Garcia-Granda, Advanced core-shell EDTA-functionalized magnetite nanoparticles for rapid and efficient magnetic solid phase extraction of heavy metals from water samples prior to the multi-element determination by ICP-OES, *Microchim. Acta* 187 (2020) 289.
- [63] M.O. Corapcioglu, C.P. Huang, The adsorption of heavy metals onto hydrous activated carbon, *Water Res.* 21 (1987) 1031–1044.
- [64] M.N. Abbas, F.S. Abbas, Utilization of Iraqi Rice husk in the removal of heavy metals from wastewater, *RJEES* 5 (2013) 370–380.
- [65] D. Ozdes, A. Gundogdu, B. Kemer, C. Duran, M. Kucuk, M. Soyлак, Assessment of kinetics, thermodynamics and equilibrium parameters of Cr(VI) biosorption onto *Pinus brutia* ten, the, *Can. J. Chem. Eng.* 92 (2014) 139–147.
- [66] T.C. Egbosuba, A.S. Abdulkareem, J.O. Tijani, J.I. Ani, V. Krikstolaityte, M. Srinivasan, A. Veksha, G. Lisak, Taguchi optimization design of diameter-controlled synthesis of multi walled carbon nanotubes for the adsorption of Pb(II) and Ni(II) from chemical industry wastewater, *Chemosphere* 266 (2021) 128937.
- [67] B. Chen, H. Guan, Y. Zhang, S. Liu, B. Zhao, C. Zhong, H. Zhang, W. Ding, A. Song, D. Zhu, L. Liu, B. Wulan, H. Li, G. Liu, X. Feng, Performance and mechanism of Pb²⁺ and Cd²⁺ ions' adsorption via modified antibiotic residue-based hydrochar, *Heliyon* 9 (2023).
- [68] H. Farrah, W.F. Pickering, pH effects in the adsorption of heavy metal ions by clays, *Chem. Geol.* 25 (1979) 317–326, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0009-2541\(79\)90063-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/0009-2541(79)90063-9).
- [69] J. Huang, F. Yuan, G. Zeng, X. Li, Y. Gu, L. Shi, W. Liu, Y. Shi, Influence of pH on heavy metal speciation and removal from wastewater using micellar-enhanced ultrafiltration, *Chemosphere* 173 (2017) 199–206.
- [70] G. Blázquez, F. Hernández, M. Calero, M.A. Martín-Lara, G. Tenorio, The effect of pH on the biosorption of Cr (III) and Cr (VI) with olive stone, *Chem. Eng. J.* 148 (2009) 473–479.
- [71] C.-Y. Cao, P. Li, J. Qu, Z.-F. Dou, W.-S. Yan, J.-F. Zhu, Z.-Y. Wu, W.-G. Song, High adsorption capacity and the key role of carbonate groups for heavy metal ion removal by basic aluminum carbonate porous nanospheres, *J. Mater. Chem.* 22 (2012) 19898.
- [72] Y. Xu, Y. Zhou, R. Li, Simultaneous fluorescence response and adsorption of functionalized Fe₃O₄@SiO₂ nanoparticles to Cd²⁺, Zn²⁺ and Cu²⁺, *Colloids Surf. A Physicochem. Eng. Asp.* 459 (2014) 240–246.
- [73] S. Tripathi, R. Bose, A. Roy, S. Nair, N. Ravishanker, Synthesis of hollow nanotubes of Zn₂SiO₄ or SiO₂: mechanistic understanding and uranium adsorption behavior, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* 7 (2015) 26430–26436.
- [74] J. Nyirenda, G. Kalaba, O. Munyati, Synthesis and characterization of an activated carbon-supported silver-silica nanocomposite for adsorption of heavy metal ions from water, *Results Eng.* 15 (2022) 100553.
- [75] C. Ray, P.C. Chan, Heavy metals in landfill leachate, *Int. J. Environ. Stud.* 27 (1986) 225–237.
- [76] P. Francesca, M. Sara, T. Luigi, New biosorbent materials for heavy metal removal: product development guided by active site characterization, *Water Res.* 42 (2008) 2953–2962.
- [77] A.A. Mamun, Z. Alam, N.a.N. Mohd, S.S. Rashid, Adsorption of heavy metal from landfill leachate by wasted biosolids, *Afr. J. Biotechnol.* 10 (2011) 18869–18881.
- [78] D. Jiang, Y. Yang, C. Huang, M. Huang, J. Chen, T. Rao, X. Ran, Removal of the heavy metal ion nickel (II) via an adsorption method using flower globular magnesium hydroxide, *J. Hazard. Mater.* 373 (2019) 131–140.
- [79] M. Mone, D.A. Lambropoulou, D.N. Bikiaris, G. Kyzas, Chitosan grafted with biobased 5-hydroxymethyl-furfural as adsorbent for copper and cadmium ions removal, *Polymers* 12 (2020) 1173.
- [80] G.O. Achieng, C.O. Kowenje, J.O. Lalah, S.O. Ojwach, Preparation, characterization of fish scales biochar and their applications in the removal of

- anionic indigo carmine dye from aqueous solutions, *Water Sci. Technol.* 80 (2020) 2218–2231.
- [81] H.M. Nguyen, K.A. Tran, T.T.N. Nguyen, N.N.H. Do, K.A. Le, P.K. Le, Fabrication of carbon aerogels from coir for oil adsorption, *IOP Conf. Ser. Earth Environ. Sci.* 964 (2022) 012033.
- [82] B. Cho, D. Kim, T. Kim, Exceptional properties of hyper-resistant armor of a hydrothermal vent crab, *Sci. Rep.* 12 (2022) 11816.
- [83] Y. Zhou, L. Ge, N. Fan, M. Xia, Adsorption of Congo red from aqueous solution onto shrimp shell powder - Youzhou Zhou, Liuqin Ge, Neng Fan, Meisheng Xia, *Adsorpt. Sci. Technol.* 36 (2018) 1310–1330 (n.d.).
- [84] S. Polat, P. Sayan, Assessment of propionic acid adsorption performance on the phase transformation of calcium sulfate hemihydrate to dihydrate, *Sep. Sci. Technol.* 53 (2018) 1966–1978.
- [85] A.M.P. Peedikakkal, I.H. Aljundi, Mixed-metal Cu-BTC metal-organic frameworks as a strong adsorbent for molecular hydrogen at low temperatures, *ACS Omega* 5 (2020) 28493–28499.
- [86] M. Inyang, B. Gao, Y. Yao, Y. Xue, A.R. Zimmerman, P. Pullammanappallil, X. Cao, Removal of heavy metals from aqueous solution by biochars derived from anaerobically digested biomass, *Bioresour. Technol.* 110 (2012) 50–56.
- [87] A. Sakly, N. Lefi, M. Bouzid, Md.M. Rahman, S. Knani, B. Graba, A.B. Lamine, Investigation of adsorption isotherms of methylene blue dye on the newly fabricated composite of nanofibers sericin/ β -cyclodextrin/PVA (PVA-SS-CD): steric and energetic interpretation, *Appl. Mater. Today* 45 (2025) 102843.
- [88] K.Y. Foo, B.H. Hameed, Insights into the modeling of adsorption isotherm systems, *Chem. Eng. J.* 156 (2010) 2–10.
- [89] K. Kadirvelu, C. Faur-Brasquet, P.L. Cloirec, Removal of Cu(II), Pb(II), and Ni(II) by adsorption onto activated carbon cloths, *Langmuir* 16 (2000) 8404–8409.
- [90] J.S. Al-Jariri, F. Khalili, Adsorption of Zn(II), Pb(II), Cr(III) and Mn(II) from water by Jordanian bentonite, *Desalin. Water Treat.* 21 (2010) 308–322.
- [91] T.A. Elbana, H. Magdi Selim, N. Akrami, A. Newman, S.M. Shaheen, J. Rinklebe, Freundlich sorption parameters for cadmium, copper, nickel, lead, and zinc for different soils: influence of kinetics, *Geoderma* 324 (2018) 80–88.
- [92] K. Kadirvelu, Adsorption of nickel(II) from aqueous solution onto activated carbon prepared from coirpith, *Sep. Purif. Technol.* 24 (2001) 497–505.
- [93] M.B. Desta, Batch sorption experiments: Langmuir and Freundlich isotherm studies for the adsorption of textile metal ions onto teff straw (*Eragrostis tef*) agricultural waste, *J. Thermodyn.* 2013 (2013) 375830.
- [94] C.S.T. Araújo, I.L.S. Almeida, H.C. Rezende, S.M.L.O. Marcionilio, J.J.L. Léon, T. N. De Matos, Elucidation of mechanism involved in adsorption of Pb(II) onto lobeira fruit (*Solanum lycocarpum*) using Langmuir, Freundlich and Temkin isotherms, *Microchem. J.* 137 (2018) 348–354.
- [95] W.W.F. Chong, M. Teodorescu, H. Rahnejat, Physio-chemical hydrodynamic mechanism underlying the formation of thin adsorbed boundary films, *Faraday Discuss.* 156 (2012) 123–136.
- [96] S. Enferadi, M. Eftekhari, M. Gheibi, N.N. Moghaddam, S. Wacławek, K. Behzadian, Modelling and optimising the performance of graphene oxide-Cu₂SnS₃-polyaniline nanocomposite as an adsorbent for mercury ion removal, *Environ. Sci. Pollut. Res.* 31 (2024) 38196–38216.
- [97] F.P. Rotzinger, J.M. Kesselman-Truttman, S.J. Hug, V. Shklover, M. Grätzel, Structure and vibrational Spectrum of Formate and acetate adsorbed from aqueous solution onto the TiO₂ rutile (110) surface, *J. Phys. Chem. B* 108 (2004) 5004–5017.
- [98] T. Şahan, Application of RSM for Pb(II) and Cu(II) adsorption by bentonite enriched with SH groups and a binary system study, *J. Water Process Eng.* 31 (2019) 100867.
- [99] A. Mohrazi, R. Ghasemi-Fasaei, A. Mojiri, S. Safarzadeh, Identification of influential parameters and conditions in heavy metals adsorption onto Cal-LDH-PC using optimization approaches of RSM and Taguchi, *Sci. Rep.* 14 (2024) 13225.
- [100] U.M.R. Paturi, S.K.P. Kolluru, S.D.S.A. Kalvakolanu, Prediction of weld-line width and sink-mark depth of plastic injection moulded parts using neural networks, *Mater. Today Proc.* (2023).
- [101] S. Jeyakrishnan, S. Vijayakumar, Naga Swapna Sri, M.P. Anusha, An integration of RSM and ANN modelling approach for prediction of FSW joint properties in AA7178/AA5456 alloys, *Can. Metall. Q.* 64 (2025) 43–60.
- [102] B.J. Claude, M.S. Onyango, Predictive modeling of copper (II) adsorption from aqueous solutions by sawdust: a comparative analysis of adaptive neuro-fuzzy interference system (ANFIS) and artificial neural network (ANN) approaches, *J. Environ. Sci. Health A* 59 (2024) 172–179.
- [103] R. Juturu, V.R. Murty, R. Selvaraj, Efficient adsorption of Cr (VI) onto hematite nanoparticles: ANN, ANFIS modelling, isotherm, kinetic, thermodynamic studies and mechanistic insights, *Chemosphere* 349 (2024) 140731.
- [104] F. Han, A.S. Hessen, A. Amari, N. Elboughdiri, S. Zahmatkesh, Heavy metal (Cu²⁺) removal from wastewater by metal-organic framework composite adsorbent: simulation-based- artificial neural network and response surface methodology, *Environ. Res.* 245 (2024) 117972.
- [105] O. US EPA, Sustainable Materials Management. <https://www.epa.gov/smm>, 2015 (accessed June 24, 2025).
- [106] X. Liu, R. Ma, X. Wang, Y. Ma, Y. Yang, L. Zhuang, S. Zhang, R. Jehan, J. Chen, X. Wang, Graphene oxide-based materials for efficient removal of heavy metal ions from aqueous solution: a review, *Environ. Pollut.* 252 (2019) 62–73.
- [107] G.Z. Whitten, The chemistry of smog formation: a review of current knowledge, *Environ. Int.* 9 (1983) 447–463.
- [108] C. Schulze, A. Jödicke, M. Scheringer, M. Margni, O. Jolliet, K. Hungerbühler, M. Matthies, Comparison of different life-cycle impact assessment methods for aquatic ecotoxicity, *Environ. Toxicol. Chem.* 20 (2001) 2122–2132.
- [109] Y.-C. Jang, T.G. Townsend, Occurrence of organic pollutants in recovered soil fines from construction and demolition waste, *Waste Manag.* 21 (2001) 703–715.
- [110] P.D. Vuyst, P. Dumortier, G.M. Swaen, J.C. Pairon, P. Brochard, Respiratory health effects of man-made vitreous (mineral) fibres, *Eur. Respir. J.* 8 (1995) 2149–2173.
- [111] L. Serrano-Luján, S. Víctor-Román, C. Toledo, O. Sanahuja-Parejo, A.E. Mansour, J. Abad, A. Amassian, A.M. Benito, W.K. Maser, A. Urbina, Environmental impact of the production of graphene oxide and reduced graphene oxide, *SN Appl. Sci.* 1 (2019) 179.
- [112] P.J. Davies, I.A. Wright, O.J. Jonasson, S.J., Findlay, Impact of concrete and PVC pipes on urban water chemistry, *Urban Water J.* 7 (2010) 233–241.
- [113] Y. Deng, J. Li, M. Qiu, F. Yang, J. Zhang, C. Yuan, Deriving characterization factors on freshwater ecotoxicity of graphene oxide nanomaterial for life cycle impact assessment, *Int. J. Life Cycle Assess.* 22 (2017) 222–236.